

Erodibility Status of Some Soils in Akoko-Edo Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Due to the detrimental effect of water erosion, erosion data must be gathered for sustenance of soil structure and utilization. The aim of the study was to determine the erodibility status of the some soils in Akoko-Edo Local Government Area of Edo state, Nigeria. Soil samples were taken from representative pedons dug from the three communities namely Ikpeshi, Unem-Nekhwa and Ososo. The samples were subjected to routine analysis and results were used to calculate the erodibility indices of Clay Dispersion Ration (CDR), Clay Disperion Index (CDI), Clay Flocculation Index (CFI) and Bouyoucous Erodibility Index (EI_{ROM}). The data derived were subjected to statistical analysis, to determine mean separation at 5% probability, coefficient of variation and standard error. The results showed that the soils were dominated by the sand fraction, mainly sandy loam with clay increment down the horizons becoming loamy sand and sandy clay loam. Soil pH ranged from an average of 5.36 – 5.62 across the pedons. Electrical Conductivity (EC) mean across the pedons ranged from 23.88 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (0.02388 dS/m) - 36.11 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ (0.0361 dS/m) which posed no salinity threat. Organic matter was low with average of 9.28 – 14.85 g/kg across the pedons. Across the horizons, the CDR ranged from 53.7 - 62.3%, CDI (42.5 - 59.2%), CFI (34.52 - 43.1%) and EI_{ROM} (1.92 - 3.93). Clay had highly significant negative correlation ($r = -0.7235$) with CDI and EI_{ROM} ($r = -0.9730$). Sand had positive correlation with CDI ($r = 0.7597$) and EI_{ROM} ($r = 0.9130$). CDR also had a positive correlation ($r = 0.8306$) with CDI. CDI had a positive correlation ($r = 0.6945$) with EI_{ROM} . Variation for all index was low, ranging from 0.1-3. The result shows that the soils are erodible and sustainable and conservational agriculture practice should be carried out.

Keywords: Akoko-Edo, erodibility, Edo state, Nigeria, status

Introduction

The need to gather information on soil conditions cannot be overemphasized, as there is an up rise in the use of land indiscriminately and also misappropriate land use systems. Soil erosion is dependent on erosivity by rainfall and the erodibility which is the resistance of the soil to destruction by external forces. The erodibility of any soils depends on the soil type, texture, level of aggregation, infiltration rate etc. Areas like Ogbogoro community in Bayelsa

State, devoid of soil erodibility data are currently in distress, as the area is ravaged by severe erosion.

As stated by Nyakatawa *et al.* (2001), soil erosion is a major environmental problem worldwide.

More than 56 % of land degradation is caused by soil erosion, raising a global concern on land productivity (Elirehema, 2001). Water erosion conveys soils, its nutrients, pesticides and other harmful chemicals into nearby rivers, streams and eventually polluting groundwater. Eroded soils are deposited in water bodies leading to pollution and siltation, which causes reduction of water quantity, quality, siltation and drying up of water bodies. Thus, aquatic life is threatened and eventually eliminated, while land productivity is negatively affected. Soil erosion is one of the most serious forms of land degradation in the world (Sohan and Lal, 2001).

Another problem associated with erosion include economic, political, social and environmental downturn which result from direct or indirect damages to the soil; which does not only cause severe land degradation and low soil productivity but also threatens the general health of society, sustainable development and habitation of rural areas, with the dwellers in particular (Tang, 2004; Zheng *et al.*, 2004; Jing *et al.*, 2005).

Consequently, erodibility data must be provided, in order to enable agriculturists, engineers and other land users to identify areas prone to erosion. This will enable them practice sustainable agriculture, and suitable land use systems, which will help control the soil erosion and its hazards. Hence, the study was undertaken to assess the current erodibility status of some soils in Akoko-Edo Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study sites are situated in Akoko-Edo local government area of Edo state, which has Ogori /Mangogo, Okehi, Adavi and Okene local government areas all in Kogi state to the North; Akoko South East, Akoko North East and Ose local government areas in Ondo state to the West; to the South: Owan East and Etsako west; and to the East with Etsako East.. It occupies an area of 1,371 km² (137,100 hectares) and lies between longitude 6° 06' 0" E and latitude 7° 17' 0" N.

The three areas (Ikpeshe - N 07.18674°, E 006.15456°, Unem Nekhua - N 07.33174° E 006.08360° and Ososo - N 07.40648°, E 006.25318°) were considered.

Climate

Akoko Edo Local Government area is characterized by tropical climate with an annual average rainfall amount of 1200 - 1500 mm, mean annual temperatures range of 27° C to 32° C and mean annual relative humidity ranging from 30.5 % to 94.0 %. The study area is characterized by two distinct seasons: the wet and the dry. The rainfall is at its climax in July and August with a short break in mid-August. The dry season begins early November and ends by March (Olowojoba *et al.*, 2016).

Geology

The area lies within the basement complex formation, which consists of various minerals like shale, coarse grained granite and granite gneiss etc with some outcrops visible around the entire local government area. Physiographically, the project area can be described as

situated on gentle plains of low relief in some areas of the local government while other areas are quite steep due to the presence of high hills visible in the area. (Olowojoba et al., 2016)

Fig. 1. Map of Akoko Edo Local Government Area showing study areas

Land use

The major land use system in the study area comprises of livestock farming, arable farming, and firewood/ timber exploitation. Arable farming consists of subsistence farming which is characterized by intensive and continuous cultivation. The main crops grown in the area are cassava, maize, yam, cacao, oil palm, cashew and some other economic trees for timber production.

Vegetation

The study area is in a derived savannah zone characterized with scattered trees such as *Irvingia gabonensis*, *Parkia biglobosa* (Jacq) R.Br (African Locust beans), *Citrus Sinensis* L (Orange) and grasses such as *Cymbopogon citratus* L. (Lemon grass), *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Sida acuta* Burm F. etc, with some visible rock outcrops occupying some large parts of the local government area.

Soil sampling

Three profile pits were dug, representing three mapping units/area including: Ikpeshi, Unem-Nekhwa and Oso. Soil samples were taken from each distinctive horizons of the soil

profiles according to Schoeneberger *et al.* (2012) guidelines. A total of seventeen (17) soil samples were acquired from the three pedons, and were subjected to routine and special laboratory analysis.

Laboratory analysis

Particle size distribution was determined by Bouyoucos hydrometer method (Gee and Or, 2002). Soil pH and Electrical conductivity was determined electrometrically using the glass electrode pH and EC meter in a solid-liquid (water) ratio of 1:2.5 (Hendershot et al., 1993). Organic carbons were determined using Walkley-Black wet oxidation methods (Walkley and Black, 1934). The organic matters were computed by multiplying the value of the organic carbon by a value of 2.0 by Douglas W. Pribyl (2010). Exchangeable bases were determined by the neutral ammonium acetate procedure buffered at pH 7.0 (Thomas, 1982). Exchangeable acidity was determined by a method described by McLean (1982). Soil bulk density was determined by the core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002). Total porosity (P_o) was obtained from bulk density (ρ_p) values with an assumed particle density value of (ρ_s) 2.65 gcm⁻³ as follows, Porosity (P_o) = $100 - (\rho_p/\rho_s) \times 100/1$.

Erodibility index

The new and advanced Bouyoucos (1962) erodibility index will be used to analyze the erodibility status

$$EI_{ROM} = \frac{\% SAND + \% SILT}{2 (\% CLAY)}$$

Table 1. 'ROM' Scale with regards to soil erodibility category (Roslan & Mazidah, 2002).

ROM SCALE	SOIL ERODIBILITY CATEGORY
< 1.5	Low
1.5 ~ 4.0	Moderate
4.0 ~ 8.0	High
8.0 ~ 12.0	Very high
> 12.0	Critical

The clay-dispersion indices were calculated as follows;

Clay dispersion ratio (CDR) = $\{(\% \text{ silt} + \text{clay (H}_2\text{O)}) / \{\% \text{ silt} + \text{clay (Calgon)}\} \times 100$

Clay dispersion index (CDI) = $\{[\% \text{ clay (H}_2\text{O)}] / [\% \text{ clay (Calgon)}]\} \times 100$

Clay flocculation index (CFI) = $[\% \text{ clay (Calgon)}] - [\% \text{ clay (H}_2\text{O)}] / [\% \text{ clay (Calgon)}] \times 100$

The higher the CDR and CDI the more the ability of the soil to disperse while the higher the CFI, the better aggregated the soil. Clay dispersion ratio was used to determine the erodibility of the soils in which greater than 15% are erodible and less than 15 % are not erodible (Middleton, 1930)

Statistical Analyses

The data generated were evaluated using the Coefficient of variations as designated by Wilding *et al.* (1994) to determine the gradation of disparity among horizons of each pedon. GenStat 12th Edition application were summarized using mean, mean separation (Duncan Multiple Range Test) at 5% level of probability. The correlation matrix was used to determine the association between some selected properties of the soil.

Results and Discussions

Soil Particle Distribution

Table 2. Some soil physical properties of the study area

Horizons	Depth (cm)	Clay	g/kg		Textural Class	Bulk Density g/cm ³	porosity %
			←	→			
Ikpeshi Soils							
N 07.18674°, E 006.15456°							
Ap	0 - 24	92.70 ^e	100.00 ^a	807.30 ^b	Loamy sand	1.457 ^a	44.91 ^d
A	24 - 41	104.30 ^d	75.0 ^b	820.70 ^a	Loamy sand	1.743 ^c	34.34 ^b
Bt1	41 - 76	225.0 ^c	58.00 ^e	717.00 ^c	Sandy clay loam	1.633 ^b	38.49 ^c
Bt2	76 - 111	248.33 ^a	60.67 ^c	691.00 ^e	Sandy clay loam	1.787 ^d	32.45 ^a
Bt3	111 - 147	238.0 ^b	60.00 ^d	702.00 ^d	Sandy clay loam	1.743 ^c	34.34 ^b
	Mean	181.66	70.73	747.6		1.6726	36.91
Unem-Nekhwa							
N 07.33174° E 006.08360							
A	0 - 14	98.00 ^e	65.00 ^b	837.00 ^c	Loamy sand	1.533 ^b	42.26 ^e
AB1	14 - 40	105.00 ^d	46.00 ^e	849.00 ^b	Loamy sand	1.453 ^a	45.28 ^f
AB2	40 - 64	108.70 ^c	69.30 ^a	822.00 ^d	Loamy sand	1.563 ^c	41.13 ^d
BA	64 - 82	90.00 ^f	41.00 ^f	869.00 ^a	Sand	1.587 ^d	39.67 ^c
Bt1h	82 - 118	135.00 ^b	56.00 ^c	809.00 ^e	Sandy loam	1.673 ^f	36.98 ^b
Bt2h	188 - 193	189.30 ^a	51.00 ^d	759.70 ^f	Sandy loam	1.653 ^e	34.67 ^a
	Mean	121	54.71	824.28		1.577	39.998
Ososo soils							
N 07.40648°, E 006.25318°							
	0 - 26						
A		120.00 ^f	95.00 ^b	785.00 ^a	Sandy loam	1.283 ^a	51.73 ^e
Bw1	26 - 49	205.00 ^e	89.00 ^c	706.00 ^b	Sandy clay loam	1.567 ^c	39.62 ^b
Bw2	49 - 83	238.00 ^c	80.00 ^d	682.00 ^c	Sandy clay loam	1.683 ^d	36.63 ^a
Bw3	83 - 114	288.00 ^a	75.00 ^e	637.00 ^e	Sandy clay loam	1.587 ^c	40.33 ^c
Bw4	114 - 144	220.70 ^d	183.31 ^a	596.00 ^f	Sandy clay loam	1.607 ^c	39.25 ^b
Bw5	144 - 187	285.00 ^b	70.00 ^f	645.00 ^d	Sandy clay loam	1.423 ^b	46.25 ^d
	Mean	226.11	98.71	675.16		1.525	42.3

Mean value(s) with the same letters(s) in the column are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of probability in each location.

The result from table 2 shows that sand fraction dominated all the horizons of the Ikpeshi soils, followed by clay, and then silt. The soils had a mean of 747.6 g/kg sand, 181.66 g/kg clay and 70.73 g/kg. The sand content reduced down the horizon while the clay fraction increased downwards. The soil texture was loamy sand at the first two horizons and sandy clay loam for the remaining three horizons. The sandy and coarse nature of Ikpeshi soils is greatly related to the parent material: basement complex formation, which consists of various minerals like shale, coarse grained granite and granite gneiss (Weil and Brady, 2016). The increase in clay down the horizon indicates the process of illuviation Niu *et al.* (2015). In Ikpeshi soils, the bulk density ranged from 1.457 – 1.787 g/cm³ with an average of 1.67

g/cm^3 . The bulk density of the Ikpeshi soil was high indicating compaction, in exception of the first horizon which had been ploughed. The bulk density values affected the porosity of the soils, the horizon with low bulk density had lower porosity of 44.91% while the highest bulk density of 1.787 g/cm^3 registered a porosity of 32.45%; lower bulk density begot higher porosity while higher bulk density begot lower pore spaces.

Table 3. Selected Chemical Properties of the Pedons

Horizons	Depth (cm)	pH	EC $\mu\text{S/cm}$	Org.C g/kg	Org.M g/kg	CEC cMol/kg	ECEC
Ikpeshi Soils							
N 07.18674°, E 006.15456°							
Ap	0 - 24	4.43 ^d	20.53 ^d	11.93 ^a	20.56 ^a	2.36 ^d	3.16 ^c
A	24 - 41	5.73 ^c	24.63 ^c	4.43 ^d	7.63 ^d	2.80 ^b	3.43 ^b
Bt1	41 - 76	6.10 ^a	52.80 ^a	10.90 ^b	18.79 ^b	2.44 ^d	2.84 ^e
Bt2	76 - 111	5.96 ^b	31.73 ^b	7.93 ^c	13.67 ^c	2.61 ^c	3.04 ^d
Bt3	111 - 147	5.90 ^b	24.70 ^c	7.90 ^d	13.61 ^c	3.00 ^a	3.60 ^a
	Mean	5.62	30.88	8.6	14.85	2.64	3.21
Unem-Nekhua							
N 07.33174° E 006.08360							
A	0 - 14	4.80 ^e	17.20 ^e	2.50 ^e	4.31 ^e	2.22 ^b	3.03 ^c
AB1	14 - 40	5.60 ^c	39.3 ^a	6.30 ^c	10.86 ^c	2.44 ^b	3.24 ^a
AB2	40 - 64	5.20 ^d	20.30 ^d	6.20 ^d	10.68 ^d	2.32 ^b	2.92 ^e
BA	64 - 82	4.30 ^f	6.50 ^f	1.70 ^f	2.93 ^f	3.08 ^a	3.22 ^b
Bt1h	82 - 118	6.60 ^a	24.40 ^c	6.40 ^b	11.03 ^b	2.26 ^b	2.66 ^f
Bt2h	188 - 193	5.66 ^b	35.63 ^b	9.23 ^a	15.91 ^a	2.33 ^b	2.92 ^d
	Mean	5.36	23.88	5.38	9.28	2.44	3
Ososo soils							
N 07.40648°, E 006.25318°							
A	0 - 26	5.50 ^b	49.50 ^a	7.90 ^b	13.61 ^b	2.50 ^e	3.30 ^f
Bw1	26 - 49	5.50 ^b	40.10 ^b	8.00 ^a	13.79 ^a	3.16 ^b	3.96 ^a
Bw2	49 - 83	5.10 ^e	29.30 ^e	7.80 ^d	13.44 ^d	2.78 ^d	3.58 ^e
Bw3	83 - 114	5.60 ^a	37.40 ^c	6.90 ^e	11.89 ^e	3.34 ^a	3.94 ^b
Bw4	114 - 144	5.23 ^d	32.00 ^d	7.86 ^c	13.55 ^c	3.08 ^c	3.84 ^c
Bw5	144 - 187	5.30 ^d	28.40 ^f	6.40 ^f	11.03 ^f	3.08 ^c	3.68 ^d
	Mean	5.37	36.11	7.47	12.88	2.99	3.71

EC: Electrical Conductivity, OC-Organic Carbon, OM – Organic Matter, CEC- Cation Exchange Capacity, ECEC – Effective Cation Exchange Capacity

In Unem-Nekhua soils, the sand fraction also dominated the horizons with an average of 824.28 g/kg, followed by clay with a mean of 121 g/kg and silt 54.71 g/kg. The texture ranged from loamy sand to sand to sandy loam indicating a reduction of the sand fraction and clay increment down the horizon. Illuviation also took place in the soils. The bulk density increased down the profile with an average of 1.577 g/cm^3 and an average porosity of 39.99%

Ososo soils recorded the highest clay content with an average of 226.11 g/kg and lowest sand fraction of 675.16 g/kg, the soils were majorly sandy clay loam apart from the

first horizon. The soils had the lowest average bulk density of 1.53 g/cm^3 and highest porosity of 42.3%.

Some chemical properties of the study areas

Ikpeshi soils had a pH of 4.43 – 6.10 which is strongly acidic to slightly acidic. The high acidity could be linked to the leaching of basic cations caused by the high rainfall in the region Niu *et al.*, (2015). The electrical conductivity ranged from 20.53 – 52.80 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ with a mean of 30.88 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ (0.03088 dS/m). This value according to the Ganjegunte *et al.* (2018) places the soil less than four (<4), which is non saline, indicating that there is no obstruction to the soil structure and it poses no threat to seedlings and salt sensitive crops. Organic carbon and organic matter low to moderate with a range of 4.43 – 11.93 g/kg and 7.63 – 20.56 g/kg. The low effective cation exchange capacity ranged from 2.84 – 3.60. This concurred with the findings of Gaillyson and David (2013). The low CEC and ECEC indicated that the pedons have low activity clays and are highly weathered according to the finding of Soil Survey Staff (2014). The highly weathered soils are more susceptible to erosion due to the formation of coarse particle which encourages poor aggregation.

Unem-Nekhua soils had pH with a mean of 5.36, EC of 23.88 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ (0.02388 dS/m), Organic Carbon and Organic matter of 5.38 and 9.28 g/kg, Cation Exchange Capacity and Effective Cation Exchange Capacity of 2.44 and 3 cMol/kg while Osoyo soils recorded a mean pH of 5.37, EC of 36.11 $\mu\text{S/cm}$ (0.0361 dS/m), OC and OM of 7.47 and 12.88 g/kg; with CEC and ECEC of 2.99 and 3.71 cMol/kg. The interpretations for Unem-Nekhua and Osoyo were all similar to that of the Ikpeshi soils.

From the result in table 4, Ikpeshi soils had a Clay Dispersion Ratio (CDR) ranging from 44 – 67% with a mean of 53.5%. Variation and standard error amongst the generic horizons were low with 0.1 coefficient of variation (CV) with standard error (SE) of 0.0577. The Clay Dispersion Index (CDI) ranged from 40.4 – 52% with an average of 44.2; the coefficient of variation and standard error were 0.1 and 0.0577. The Clay Flocculation Index (CFI) ranged from 30.7 – 39.9% with a mean of 34.52, Coefficient of Variation of 0.2 and Standard error of 0.0577. The Bouyoucos Erodibility Index (EI_{ROM}) ranged from 1.52 – 4.88 with a mean of 2.80, CV of 0.9 and SE of 0.02633. The CDR, CDI, CFI and EI_{ROM} registered low variations amongst the different horizons.

The CDR of the Ikpeshi soils was far above 15% in all the horizons indicating that they are weak soil structure and are erodible. The CFI which is another factor used to determine the resistance of soils to dispersion, was also low indicating low resistance of the soils to external erodible forces. The CFI connotes the ability of the soils to aggregate; the Ikpeshi soils recorded low CFI, thus weak aggregation. The EI_{rom} on the other hand ranged from high to moderate down the horizons.

The CDR in Unem-Nekhua soils ranged from 50.5 – 77% with a mean of 62.3%, CDI (50 – 66.2%, mean – 59.2), CFI (33.5 – 40.89% with mean of 36.4) and EI_{rom} had a range of 2.3 – 5.1 with a mean of 3.90. The coefficient of variation and standard error were 0.1 for CDR, CDI, CFI respectively, 1.5 for EI_{ROM} and 0.0473 for CDR, 0.0577 for CDI, 0.0410 for CFI, & 0.0577 for EI_{ROM} . The table 4 shows that CDR and CDI were above 15% indicating that the soils are erodible, also the CFI for the different horizons were low, showing weak aggregation. The EI_{ROM} indicated that the erodibility was high to moderate.

Table 4. Erodibility indices of the study areas

Horizons	Depth (cm)	CDR ←———— % —————→	CDI	CFI	EI _{ROM}
Ikpeshi Soils					
N 07.18674°, E 006.15456°					
Ap	0 - 24	67 ^e	52 ^d	39.9 ^e	4.88 ^e
A	24 - 41	44 ^a	40.4a	30.7a	4.31d
Bt1	41 - 76	57.4 ^d	45.8 ^c	35.7 ^d	1.72 ^c
Bt2	76 - 111	51.1 ^c	42.5 ^b	33.3 ^c	1.52 ^a
Bt3	111 - 147	49 ^b	40.3 ^a	33 ^b	1.6 ^b
	Mean	53.7	44.2	34.52	2.80
	CV	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.9
	SE	0.0577	0.0577	0.0577	0.02633
Unem-Nekhwa					
N 07.33174° E 006.08360					
A	0 - 14	77 ^f	66.2 ^f	34.01 ^b	4.6 ^e
AB1	14 - 40	50.52 ^a	50 ^a	40.89 ^f	4.3 ^d
AB2	40 - 64	56.8 ^b	55.1 ^b	39.02 ^e	4.1 ^c
BA	64 - 82	67.9 ^e	65.8 ^e	33.5 ^a	5.1 ^f
Bt1h	82 - 118	61.41 ^d	60.7 ^d	34.8 ^c	3.2 ^b
Bt2h	188 - 193	60 ^c	57.6 ^c	36 ^d	2.3 ^a
	Mean	62.3	59.2	36.4	3.93
	CV	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.5
	SE	0.0473	0.0577	0.0410	0.0577
Ososo soils					
N 07.40648°, E 006.25318°					
A	0 - 26	57 ^e	50.5 ^e	45.05 ^e	3.7 ^d
Bw1	26 - 49	56.2 ^d	46.9 ^d	42.6 ^d	1.9 ^c
Bw2	49 - 83	56 ^c	42.3 ^c	42 ^c	1.6 ^b
Bw3	83 - 114	56.01 ^c	40.8 ^b	41.7 ^b	1.2 ^a
Bw4	114 - 144	50.3 ^b	40.8 ^b	41.6 ^a	1.8 ^c
Bw5	144 - 187	49.3 ^a	33.7 ^a	45.8 ^f	1.3 ^a
	Mean	54.1	42.5	43.1	1.92
	CV	0.1	0.1	0.1	3.0
	SE	0.0528	0.0577	0.0528	0.0577

CV – Coefficient of Variation SE – Standard Error CDR – Clay Dispersion Ratio
 EI_{ROM} - Bouyoucos Erodibility Index CDI – Clay Dispersion Index CFI – Clay Flocculation Index

In Ososo soils, the CDR ranged from 49.3 – 57% with a mean of 54.1% , CV (0.1), and SE of 0.0528. The CDI was 33.7-50.5% with a mean of 42.5%, CV of 0.1 and SE of 0.0577. CFI ranged from 41.6 - 45.8% with a mean of 43.1%, CV of 0.1 and SE of 0.0528. EI_{ROM} ranged 1.3-3.7 with a mean value of 1.92, CV of 3.0 and SE of 0.0577. The data shows that, like the other soils, the Ososo soils are also erodible. Igwe and Udegbunam (2008), also reported that DR, CDI, and CFI were high when compared to the soils of Southern Nigeria. The result when correlated to the findings of Oguike and Mbagwu (2009) in soils of Southern Nigeria shows that DR and CDI were high while CFI was low.

Table 5 shows the correlation matrix between some erodibility indices and some selected soil physical properties. Clay had highly significant negative correlation ($r = -0.7235$) with CDI and EI_{ROM} ($r = -0.9730$). Sand had positive correlation with CDI ($r = 0.7597$) and EI_{ROM} ($r = 0.9130$). CDR also had a positive correlation ($r = 0.8306$) with CDI. CDI had a positive correlation ($r = 0.6945$) with EI_{ROM} .

Table 5. Correlation matrix of erodibility indices and some selected soil physical properties

	CLAY	SILT	SAND	CDR	CDI	CFI	EI_{ROM}
	←	g/kg	→	←	%	→	
CLAY	1						
SILT	0.1507	1					
SAND	-0.9227**	-0.5199	1				
CDR	-0.4585	-0.1878	0.4664	1			
CDI	-0.7235**	-0.3490	0.7597**	0.8306**	1		
CFI	0.2917	0.4248	-0.4167	-0.1374	-0.3473	1	
EI_{ROM}	-0.9730**	-0.1858	0.9130**	0.4918	0.6945**	-0.2713	1

Conclusion

The results of the study areas show that the soils were dominated by the sand fraction which could be attributed to the parent material, the pH was acidic to slightly acidic; the soil of the three areas recorded low electrical conductivity indicated no threat of salinity and obstruction. The organic matter and cation exchange capacity was also low. The erodibility indices used stated that the soils are erodible. This could be related to the low organic matter content and lower clay fraction, which could serve as soil binding agents and improve soil structure and aggregation. The destructive power of erosion on agriculture can never be overemphasized, hence conservation methods such as cover cropping, contour cropping, slope terracing, and conservational tillage methods etc should be practiced to control and limit soil erosion.

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References

- Bouyocous G.J. (1962). Hydrometer method improved for making particle size analysis of soil. *Agr. J.* 54: 3.
- Douglas W. P. (2010). A Critical review of the conventional SOC to SOM conversion factor. *Geoderma*, Vol. 156, Pp. 75- 83.
- Elirehema, Y.S. (2001). Soil Water Erosion Modeling in Selected Watersheds in Southern Spain. IFA, ITC, Enschede.
- Gaillyson, Y.J. and David, O.O. (2013). Soil profile characteristics as affected by land use systems in the Southeastern Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Veterinary Science*, Vol. 6 (4) 04 - 11.
- Ganjegunte, G. K, Clark J. A., Parajulee M. N., Enciso, J. and Kumar, S. (2018). Salinity management in pima cotton fields using sulfur burner. *Agrosystems, Geosciences and Environment*, 1: 180006.

Gee, G.W., Or, G. (2002). Particle size, In: Dane J.H. & Topp, G.C. (eds). *Methods of Soil analysis. Part 4 Physical methods*. Soil Science Society of America Madison, WI, Book Series No. 5 ASA and SSA 255 – 293.

Grossman, R.B., Reinsch, T.G. (2002). Bulk Density and linear extensibility. In: Dane, J.H., and Top G.C. (Eds). *Methods of soil analysis* (part 4, physical methods). (pp. 201-228). Soil Science Society of America. Book series no. 5. ASA and SSA Madison, WI, USA.

Hendershort, W.H., Lalonde, H., & Duquette, M. (1993). Soil reaction and exchangeable acidity. In: Carter M.R. (ed), *Soil Sampling and methods of soil analysis*. (pp. 141-145). Canadian Society of Soil Science, Lewis Publishers, London.

Igwe, C. A., Udegbonam, O. N. (2008). Soil properties influencing water-dispersible clay and silt in an Ultisols in Southern Nigeria. *International Agrophysics*, 22, 319 – 325.

Jing, K., Wang, W.Z. and Zheng, F.L. (2005). Soil erosion and environment in Beijing, China. Science Press.

McLean, E. O. (1982). Aluminum. In: C.A. Black (Ed.). *Methods of soil analysis*. Agron. No. 9. Part II. *Am. Soc. Agron*, Madison, Wisconsin USA.

Middleton, H. E. (1930). Properties of soils which influence soil erosion. *Tech. Bull.* no. 178. Washington, DC: USDA

Niu, D.F., Li, B.S., Wang, F.N., Wen, X.H., Ma, J.L. Shu, P.X., (2015) Climate changes indicated by the clay minerals: A case of the Dishaogouwan section on the south eastern margin of the Mu Us Desert. *Journal of Fuzhou University* (National Science Education) 43: 345–351.

Nyakatawa, E.Z., Reddy, K.C., Lemunyon, J.L. (2001). Predicting soil erosion in conservation tillage cotton production systems using the revised universal soil loss equation (RUSLE). *Soil and Tillage Research*, 57 (4), 213-224.

Oguike, P. C., Mbagwu, J. S. C. (2009). Variations in some physical properties and organic matter content of soils of coastal plain sand under different land use types. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 5 (1): 63 – 69.

Olowjoba S.O., Kappo A.A., Ogbole J.O., Alaga A.T., Mohammed S.O., Eguaroje E.O. (2016). Land Suitability and Evaluation for the Production of Cassava in Akoko-Edo L.G.A. of Edo State using Geo-Technology Techniques. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 6(2): 059-068, <http://doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2016.2.011416008>

Schoeneberger, P.J., Wysocki D.A., Benham E.C., (2012). Field book for describing and sampling soils, Version 3.0. Natural Resources Conservation Service, National Soil Survey Center, Lincoln, NE.

Sohan, W., Lal, S. (2001). Extraction of parameters and modeling soil erosion using GIS in an arid environment. Center for Remote Imaging, *Sensing and Processing*.

Soil Survey Staff. (2014). Soil Survey Field and Laboratory Methods Manual. Soil Survey Investigations Report No. 51, Version 2.0. R. Burt and Soil Survey Staff (ed.). U.S. Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service.

Tang, K.L. (Ed) (2004). Soil and Conservation in Beijing, China. *Science Press*.

Thomas, G. W. (1982). Exchangeable Cations. In: A. L. Page; R. H. Miller and D. R. Keeney (eds.). *Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 2, Chemical and Microbiological properties*. Madison, Wisconsin. Pp. 159 – 164.

Walkley, A., Black, I.A. (1934). An examination of the different methods for determining soil organic matter and the proposed modification of the chromic acid wet titration method. *Soil Science of America Journal*. 37: 29 – 38.

Weil, R.R and Brady, N.C (2016). *The Nature and Properties of Soils*. (15th Ed) Pearson Education. ISBN: 978- 0133254488.

Wilding, L.P., Bouma, J. and Boss, D.W. (1994). Impact of spatial variability on interpretative modeling. In: *Quantitative modeling of soil forming processes*. Bryant, R.B. and Arnold, R.W. SSSA. Special Publication. No.39: 61.

Zheng, F., Stephen, D.M., Huang, C., Tanaka, D.L., Darboux, F., Liebig, M.A, Halvorson, A.D. (2004). Runoff, soil erosion and erodibility of Conservation Reserve Program land under crop and hay production. *Soil Science Society of American Journal*, Vol. 68 (4): 1332 – 1341.